

Application of Tank Silt for Improving Arecanut Productivity in Karnataka

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Introduction

The areca nut palm produces the common chewing nut, which is known as betel nut or supari. This nut is consumed to a considerable extent and has great demand. In India, areca nut is very much linked with religious practices. India is the largest producer and consumer of areca nut in the world. The areca nut is not a true nut but a fruit categorized as a drupe that belongs to the family of "Arecaceae" and the genus of "Areca L." It is commercially available in dried, cured and fresh forms. Commercial cultivation of areca nut is more successful in India.

Major Arecanut Producing States in India

Karnataka, Kerala, Assam, Tamil Nadu, Meghalaya & West Bengal are the major states growing areca nut.

Arecanut in Karnataka

Karnataka has occupied first place among areca nut growing states in India. Arecanut is grown in Karnataka as a cash crop; growers spend their entire lives developing and maintaining the crop. Arecanut cultivation is a traditional form of agriculture in the mainland and coastal parts of Karnataka. The cultivation of areca nut is concentrated in Dakshina Kannada, Uttara Kannada, Udupi, Shimoga, Chikmagalur districts of Karnataka, which receive high rainfall. Arecanut is also grown in plain land area districts like Chitradurga, Davanagere, Tumkur and in certain parts of Hassan, Mandya, Mysore and Kodagu districts. At the same time, the contribution to total

production is about 45% from coastal belt regions, 40% from the plain land area and the remaining 15% from other districts. Recently, it extended to plain lands as they are blessed with irrigation projects and channel water.

Soil and Climate Requirements for Arecanut Cultivation

Arecanut can be grown on a wide range of soils. However, this crop thrives best in well-drained soils with good organic matter. Arecanut cultivation was predominant in gravelly laterite soils of the red clay type of Southern Kerala and Coastal Karnataka. Laterite, red loam and alluvial soils are most suitable. In areas where tank irrigation is common practice, the soils may have an admixture of tank silt. Similar results were also reported by Srinivasan et al. (2021) on a coconut plantation. Soil pH from 5.2 to 7.0 is suitable for cultivation. To avoid sun-scorch, adequate protection from exposure to the South-Western sun should be needed. Quick growing shade-providing trees should be planted on the southern and western sides well before planting areca nut seedlings. This palm nut tree is sensitive to moisture deficit and should be grown where adequate irrigation is available. This crop requires a well-distributed annual rainfall of 750 mm to 4500 mm. This crop can be grown at altitudes up to 1000 meters above mean sea level (MSL). The ideal temperature range of 10°C to 40°C is best for its growth and yield.

Tank silt

Tank silt is a fine soil particle transported from the catchment area by surface runoff and soil erosion during the monsoon period along with crop debris and deposited as sediment in the tank water spread area. This silt is rich in organic matter with good physical properties. The deposited soil and crop debris will decompose over time and become nutrient-rich soil amendments. Nutrient flow in the undulated plains or watersheds; especially the leaching of soil nutrients along the water stream and accumulation in natural or manmade barriers such as tanks, ponds, ditches, lakes, and rivers is well-documented phenomenon (Balamatti and Satish, 2018).

Agriculture is a major part of the catchment areas and contributes to the tanks' rainwater storage. Many centuries ago, tanks are constructed to harvest the rainwater to offset monsoons' vagaries for irrigated agriculture. Intermittent and high-intensity rainfall during the monsoons

causes heavy surface runoff and erosion of valuable nutrient-rich topsoil from the surrounding agricultural lands. These soil particles and nutrients are deposited as silt in the tanks (Srinivasan and Thilagam, 2022).

Tanks serve the most critical purpose of conserving the prime natural resources, like soil and water, which facilitate their multiple uses, such as irrigation, flood control, groundwater recharge, and other social, economic, and ecosystem functions. However, the accumulation of silt in the tank adversely affects its storage capacity in the long run.

Soil quality improvement through tank silt application

- Tank silt hybridization improves the water holding capacity of soils.
- Applying tank silt in combination with organic manure reduces the soil bulk density.
- Application of tank silt and FYM reduce the soil pH due to organic acid production during the mineralization of organic materials.
- Enhancement of soil organic carbon content.
- Tank silt applied cropland is richer in soil available nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and micronutrients
- The application of tank silt in the soil helps retain nutrients and increase nutrient availability to the crops.
- It is an excellent organic amendment for improving water-use efficiency and productivity during low water situations.

Tank silt for Arecanut production

- The addition of tank silt to the areca nut plantation neutralizes the soil's chemical properties and improves the quality and health of soils.
- Reduce soil erosion and increase the water infiltration rate.
- The high clay content of tank silt reduces the drainage capacity of the red gravelly soils and improves the water holding capacity (Narayanan, 2015).

- Tank silt mixed with FYM, vermicompost and other fertilizers ensures the slow release of nutrients to the maize.
- Tank silt improves the soil bulk density, porosity and aeration, which helps better root development and establishment of maize.
- Unavailable form major and micronutrients are converted to available form and quickly taken up by the plant.
- Clay-humus complex improves the micronutrient status of the areca nut, increases nut productivity, and improves soil quality.
- Good soil physical condition and increased biological activity improve the nut size and yield.
- Excess root growth will be controlled by filling tank silt and improving the standing capacity of areca nut plantation over a year.

Yield in Arecanut Cultivation

In any crop, yield depends on the selected cultivar and soil/climate and farm management practices. In areca nut plantation, adding tank silt will improve the 20-30% of yield.

Root growth problem

Silt covering the root zone

Enhanced yield

Conclusions

Tank silt is a locally available and low-cost soil amendment efficient in soil and water conservation. It has multiple benefits on climate resilient farming that can be promoted on a large scale. Tank silt improves the nutrient use efficiency, soil texture, water holding capacity, soil organic carbon status, soil fertility and root proliferation in the areca nut orchard. Appropriate use of tank silt will improve the yield and quality of nuts and enhance farmers' income in different parts of Karnataka.

Reference

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